

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15862445

Evaluation Of The Implementation Of Social Studies Curriculum In Universal Basic Education In Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria

Umar Usman & Prof. David Amokaha Aboho

**Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education
Taraba State University, Jalingo, Nigeria.**

ABSTRACT

The study evaluated Implementation of Social Studies curriculum in Universal Basic Education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. Specifically, the study evaluated the extent to which students develop positive attitude with implementation of Social Studies curriculum, the extent to which social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented, the pedagogical methods used by social studies teachers in the implementation of the social studies curriculum Two research questions guided the study and two research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of this study consist of 1445 Social Studies Teachers in the 52 junior secondary schools in Jalingo Education Zone. While the sample for the study was 376, teachers drawn randomly from all the three LGAs in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State. Structured questionnaire titled 'Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum Basic Education programme questionnaire (ISSCBEPQ) and Social Studies Curriculum Content Coverage Checklist (SSCCCC) were duly validated and used as instrument for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was obtained by subjecting the instrument to a pilot test and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.859. Descriptive statistics of mean, and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while Chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the analysis of the data, the findings revealed that implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of the UBE in Junior Secondary Schools develops students' positive attitude, result also implies that social study curriculum content is adequately covered, different pedagogical methods are used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools and Social Studies teachers use instructional materials in the implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo education zone. It was concluded that the implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE has significant implications for the educational development in Jalingo Education zone. The study recommends among others that Regular retraining through seminars, symposia and workshops should be organized for Social Studies teachers by State Universal Basic Education to update their knowledge in the implementation of Social Studies UBE curriculum for the realization of learning objectives as room still exists for improvements.

Keywords: Social Studies curriculum, Junior Secondary Schools, UBE

INTRODUCTION

One of the major outcomes of the committee was changes in Social Studies curriculum. The innovation carried out was both organizational and pedagogical in nature. In compliance with the Universal Basic Education, the curriculum scope covers primary one to junior secondary school using a spiral model of curriculum design. In the same perspective, Gabriel (2018) posits that Social Studies was integrated into the Nigerian school curriculum to restore Nigeria from all sorts of social vices and to encourage Nigerians towards becoming good citizens who would help the country realize her national goals and objectives.

Presently, Social Studies curriculum is designed according to the goals of Universal Basic Education (UBE). The Universal Basic Education is the type of education that is given compulsorily in the first level of education. Eya (2012) posits that Universal Basic Education is a kind of educational programme that is intended to be universal, free and compulsory. The Federal Ministry of Education (2014) defines Universal Basic Education as a type of education comprising six years of primary education and three years of junior secondary school which provides learners with reading, writing and numerical skills. The vision of the Universal Basic Education is that at the end of nine years of continuous education, every child should have acquired appropriate and relevant skills and values and be employable in order to contribute his/her quota to national development. Thus, for the vision of the UBE programme to be achieved, its curriculum structure must be embraced at all levels because basic education is required for self-reliance for those it is meant for.

Social Studies is an organized and integrated study of man and his physical and social environment. It is intended to help him acquire skills, attitudes and actions for the purpose of creating effective citizenry. Social Studies also refers to a school subject that inculcates the right type of virtues in the learner through united and interdisciplinary studies. The National Council for Social Studies (2019) states that Social Studies is an integrated study of the social sciences and humanities to promote civic competence within the school programme thus, Social studies provides coordinated, systematic study drawing upon such disciplines as anthropology, archaeology, economics, geography, history, political science and psychology.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) states that there are a number of objectives of Social Studies Universal Basic Education curriculum especially for upper Basic secondary school programme. These are to: “make students aware of the problems of their country, and to appreciate interdependence between people; create an awareness and understanding of the evolving social and physical environment, its natural, man-made, cultural and spiritual resources together with the rational use and conservation of these resources for development; develop in students a positive attitude to citizenship and a desire in them to make a positive personal contribution to the creation of a united Nigeria”. It is also aimed at developing a capacity to learn and acquire skills essential to the formation of a satisfactory professional; developing in students an appreciation of their cultural heritage and a desire to preserve it; acquiring, developing and inculcating the proper value-orientation for the survival of the individual and society; and acquiring both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community.

The concern of this study is to evaluate the implementation of Social Studies curriculum in Universal Basic Education, in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. Curriculum implementation is aimed at actualizing the planned curriculum. It is the translation of the curriculum contents (objectives) into practice or action. Nzewi, Okpara and Akudolu (2015) note that implementation of curriculum is normally done in the classroom through joint efforts of the teacher and the learner and those concerned.

The evaluation of implementation of Social Studies for Universal Basic Education curriculum is expected to help reposition Social Studies teaching and learning process to achieve set objectives. Ololobou (2017) defines evaluation as the collection and use of information as a basis for rational decision-making on the curriculum. According to Weiss (2018) evaluation is a systematic process to understand what a programme does and how well the programme does it. Evaluation results can be used to maintain or improve programme quality and to ensure that future planning can be more evidence-based. Evaluation constitutes part of an on-going cycle of programme planning, implementation and improvement. This

decision, therefore, could help to improve on the implementation which will lead to the attainment of the set objectives of Universal Basic Education Social Studies curriculum.

Ironically, Social Studies has been implemented many years now without adequate success in terms of inculcating the right type of attitudes and values of good citizenship among the youths (Abdu-Raheem, 2012). The youths are rich in knowledge of Social Studies concepts and facts but deficient in expected social values, attitudes and behaviours that characterize socially responsible citizens (Adeyemi & Ajibade, 2016). It may be assumed that the deficiency arose from the way the subject was taught and learnt in the classroom. Okam (2018) found that teachers' use of lecture method in teaching the subject that required interactive methods in a conducive social environment was responsible. The author explains further that a teacher is expected to be a facilitator whose main function is to help learners to become active participants in their learning. Even when teaching is effective or not there is need to have a way of evaluating what is being done.

The implication of this for the educational development of Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is that it is expected that the teaching and learning experiences to be acquired through Social Studies should be such that will make the learners develop the ability to adapt to changing environment, national consciousness and spirit of national unity, ethics of good citizenship and the willingness to contribute to the development of the society as well as acquire the right types of values and attitudes. Furthermore, Federal Ministry of Education (2014) notes that in order to acquire the right type of values and attitudes from the contents of learning, the spiral approach capable of addressing the issues of value re-orientation, poverty eradication, peace and dialogue, family life, HIV and AIDS education, critical thinking and life coping skills was adopted. These contents represent part of the total experiences to which all learners must be exposed and the minimum knowledge, attitude and values required to be developed for the achievement of the objectives of the Social Studies Universal Basic Education curriculum.

The content of Social Studies is organized around social environment issues affecting man's existence and ability to perform and conserve the environment (Ezeoba and Okafor, 2019). They further noted that the curriculum content of Social Studies is aimed at achieving the objectives of Social Studies. According to Akubuilu, et al (2019) and Akubuilu, Ugo, Ugo, Ugochukwu & Ikehi, (2019) teachers, coverage of Social Studies content is a vital aspect of curriculum implementation. According to Ezeoba and Okafor (2019) its implementation touches every sphere of society.

Thus, the ingredients for Social Studies in the curriculum have failed to enable students to develop an understanding of their societal values and knowledge, values and skills that would enable them to deal with social problems. Iheoma (2015) states that school subjects have perhaps not achieved the aims of transmitting moral and societal values in the youths because the current methods and techniques adopted for moral education in Nigerian schools are inadequate to cope with moral crises in the society. The author has also observed that the poor implementation of Social Studies curriculum in schools today seems to create more problems in the society. Hence the need for this study to evaluate the implementation of Social Studies curriculum in Universal Basic Education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State.

Statement of Problem

Social Studies Curriculum of Universal Basic Education Programme as a policy document and academic programme was introduced to educational system in Nigeria with the aim of inculcating positive values and building of better Nigeria. This is encapsulated in the objectives of Social Studies curriculum which include making students aware of the problems of their country and to appreciate interdependence between people; developing a positive attitude to citizenship and a desire in them to make a positive personal contribution to the creation of united Nigeria. Furthermore, it is aimed at developing in students an appreciation of their cultural heritage and a desire to preserve it as well as acquisition and development of proper value-orientation for the survival of the individual and society. The course should lead to the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the society. This could be possible only when there is effective implementation of social studies curriculum at all levels of education.

However, there is an indication that Social Studies curriculum for Universal Basic Education programme seem not been properly implemented in schools particularly in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State to equip students with the necessary knowledge, facts and ideas that can enhance positive values and attitudes for the survival of individuals and the society. It seems like the poor or non-implementation of the Social Studies Universal Basic Education Curriculum could be responsible for the prevalence of social vices in the zone. That is why social problems range from disrespect to elders and constituted authorities, chronic dishonesty, corruption, religious crisis, ethnic/tribal crisis, murder, arson, examination malpractices, drug abuse, cultism, indiscipline, kidnapping are common in the zone. It is therefore, against this backdrop that this study seeks to evaluate the Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum in Universal Basic Education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the Implementation of Social Studies curriculum in Universal Basic Education in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State. The study specifically seeks to:

1. Determine the extent to which social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State.
2. Ascertain the pedagogical methods used by social studies teachers in the implementation of the social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent is social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State?
2. What are the pedagogical methods used by social studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant

H01: The extent to which social studies curriculum content of Universal Basic Education is being implemented in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state is not significant.

H02: The pedagogical methods used by social studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of Universal Basic Education in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is not significant.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Dror's Lour (1973) theory of evaluation, Schon's (1971) curriculum implementation model and Chrisis (1968) curriculum implementation models

Theory of Evaluation by Dror's Lour (1973)

The theory of evaluation was propounded by Dror in 1973. The theory assumes that there are two categories of evaluation that could be used in making judgment. These are: primary and secondary evaluations. The primary category is used in a business firm which exists to make profit and money which can be counted or measured. The primary category is not feasible in education. The secondary category is the process pattern, the category that use evaluation in education. The process pattern determines if the process which delivers the end result in the implementation of the educational programme is as good as it should be. The secondary category is unified and can be used to underpin this study because it is applicable in several activities including Universal Basic Education programme.

Curriculum Implementation Model by Ann'rou Schon's (1971)

The Curriculum implementation model was postulated by Schon in 1971. The model classifies implementation model into three different ways of disseminating innovation for implementation. They are: (1) The centre periphery (C-P) model, (2) the proliferation of the centre (P-C) model and (3) the periphery centre or shifting centre model.

The Centre Periphery (C-P) Model

In this model, the innovative programmes are developed by experts such as officials of ministries and examiners who act at the centre. The new ideas are disseminated to schools for implementation. The success of the project depends on the effectiveness at the centre, the level of resources available and how effectively the resources are well managed.

The Proliferation of the Centre (C-P) Model

This includes primary and secondary centres. The primary centre is supportive and manages the secondary centre. It is the secondary centre that is engaged in the diffusion of innovation. It is the facilitator and has no rigid control over the primary centre. The effectiveness of this approach depends to a large extent on the ability of the primary centres to generate support and manage auxiliary centres, the availability of well trained workers in the outpost.

The Periphery Centre or Shifting Centres Model

This model does not suffer from dependence on limited resources and competence and from undue rigidity of a central doctrine. Problems are assessed on their merit and where there is need for reform, this is disseminated to the central agency which makes input on how to overcome the problem. Schon's curriculum implementation model is related to this study as it deals with how the programmes are developed by experts such as officials of ministries and examiners. New ideas are disseminated to schools for implementation. Problems are assessed on their merit. The models discussed above is a guiding principle towards effective curriculum implementation, this explains how relevant Schon curriculum implementation model is to this study. This model is related to this study as it gives room for flexibility which is one of the characteristics of curriculum and therefore aid teaching and learning of Social studies. To this model the process of evaluation includes the evaluation of instruction. It includes the evaluation of instructional materials, teachers, teaching methods and students' learning. That is conducting evaluation on teachers' instructional materials, methods, students-teacher interaction, classroom management, teachers' characteristics, teachers' performance in the classroom and other dynamics of the teaching-learning situation which is related to Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum.

Empirical Studies

Francis (2016) assessed the implementation of social studies curriculum for effective citizenship in primary schools in Kaduna State. The main focus of this work is to find out the roles of government in achieving social studies curriculum objective, methods to be used in teaching and learning social studies at primary school level and the issue of teacher qualification effect in teaching social studies for effective citizenship in primary schools in Kaduna State. He adopted survey design with population of 5552 primary school students and teachers and the sample of 357 students and teachers using Krejcie and Morgan formula. The findings of his work disclosed that the role of government and supervision on the implementation of the objectives of social studies curriculum has significant impact on effect of citizenship of pupils in primary schools, the methods of teaching techniques that aids learning in social studies have tremendous effect on effective citizenship of pupils in primary schools and the teachers' qualification determines the level of achievement of social studies curriculum objectives for effective citizenship of pupils in schools.

The study under review is in line with the present study in the design, population of study and statistics used in data analysis. Even though the studies vary in the sampling procedure, scope of study, area of study, and instrument for data collection, in which the study under review make used of adapted questionnaire while the present study will used self-constructed questionnaire and social studies curriculum content coverage checklist

Adoke (2017) studied teachers and students perceptions of social studies and teaching methods in selected junior secondary schools in the northern states of Nigeria using total of 2015 students and 160 teachers. The focus of this research work is to ascertain the methods used by social studies teachers, the availability of social studies teaching materials and the trained and adequate social studies teachers in selected junior secondary schools in the northern states of Nigeria. Survey design was adopted in carrying out the

research and while questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. It was discovered that methods mainly employed were discussion and story telling methods while the problem solving approach, group method and the use of resource persons ranked the least. Furthermore, lack of trained teachers and inadequate textbooks were predominant.

The study under review is related to present study in the design instrument for data collection and model of testing reliability on the other hand the studies varies in the area of study, scope of study, sampling procedure and population of the study. Because the study under review was carry out in northern state, Nigeria. The current study was conducted in Taraba state Nigeria, in terms of scope the study under review covers a large scope of northern state, while the present study covers Jalingo education zone, in Taraba state.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A Descriptive Survey Research Design was employed for this study. The population of this study consist of all the Social Studies Teachers in the 52 Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone of Taraba State. Social Studies Teachers population as at the time that this study was conducted is 1445. The sample size for this study was determined using formula suggested by Taro Yamane as cited in Israel (2013). The assumption is that the sample is representative of the population. $n = 313$. The sample size for this study is three hundred and thirteen (313) social studies teachers. Israel (2013) advised that 10% - 30% should be added to the sample size. Sixty-three (63) respondents which is 20% of the sample size were added to the calculated sample size of 313 bringing it to 376, therefore 376 copies of the questionnaire was administered across the zone. Multi-stage sampling was used to select the sample size for the study, in the first stage, the secondary schools for the study were grouped along local government areas. For even representation, simple random sampling (lettering) procedure is used to select twenty one from Jalingo, nine from Ardo kola and five secondary schools from Lau in the zone. This was done to accommodate local government areas with few secondary schools in which total of thirty-five (35) junior secondary schools were selected in the zone.

Two instruments used for data collection in this study were: a self-developed structured questionnaire by the researcher, titled 'Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum Basic Education Programme Questionnaire (ISSCBEPQ) and Social Studies Curriculum Content Coverage Checklist (SSCCCC). The items are made on a four point Likert scale of Very High Extent, (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). To determine the validity of the instrument initial copies of the instrument with purpose and items were submitted to three experts one from educational measurement evaluation, one from educational foundations and one from science education in the Faculty of Education, Taraba State University. The validated instrument were administered to a sample of forty teachers randomly selected from three junior secondary schools in Zing Education Zone. The reliability coefficient of 0.859 was obtained and this is considered reliable in line with the assertion of Ajai and Amuche. 2015. Descriptive statistics of means and standard deviations was used in answering the research questions. Allocations of scores to scales are 4, 3, 2 and 1 for responses VHE, HE, LE and VLE respectively for items designated as positive (+) scale while 1, 2, 3 and 4 responses designated as negative (-) scale.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

The data collected using the instruments developed for the study are presented and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while chi-square was used to test the hypotheses.

Research Question One: *To what extent is social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of extent to which social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools

S/N	Content	N	Adequately Covered Freq (%)	Partly Covered Freq (%)	Not Covered Freq (%)	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1	General Objectives of Social Studies	35	14(40)	6(17.1)	15(42.9)	1.97	.92	Not Covered
2	Family Bond and Living Together as one Family	35	16(45.7)	4(11.4)	15(42.9)	2.03	.95	Covered
3	Purpose of Marriage	35	21(60)	9(25.7)	5(14.3)	2.46	.74	Covered
4	Readiness in Marriage	35	17(48.6)	12(34.3)	6(17.1)	2.31	.76	Covered
5	Positive Behaviour	35	13(37.1)	13(37.1)	9(25.7)	2.11	.80	Covered
6	Meaning and Consequences of drug abuse and harmful substances	35	13(37.1)	13(37.1)	9(25.7)	2.11	.80	Covered
7	Dangers of drug trafficking	35	13(37.1)	11(31.4)	11(31.4)	2.06	.84	Covered
Grand Mean/Std Dev.		35				2.15	0.83	Covered

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 above reveals responses on the extent to which social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools. All the items except item 1 have their means above 2.00; this shows that the extent to which social studies curriculum content of UBE is being implemented in Junior Secondary Schools is high. The cluster has a mean of 2.15 and a standard deviation of 0.83; the result also implies that social studies curriculum content is adequately covered.

Research Question Two: *What are the pedagogical methods used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of Social Studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of the Pedagogical Methods Used by Social Studies Teachers in the Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Social studies teachers often use traditional methods of teaching.	3.16	0.93	Agree
2	Social studies students learn better when modern methods and strategies of teaching are use.	3.58	0.59	Agree
3	Social studies teachers often use modern technique as teaching strategies.	2.59	1.10	Agree
4	The students become more interested in the lesson when teachers apply learner-centered approach in teaching social studies.	3.63	0.48	Agree
5	Social studies teachers present their lesson using new pedagogical approach.	2.65	1.11	Agree
6	Social studies teachers always interested in using new methods and strategies of teaching during the lesson.	2.80	1.19	Agree
7	There are adequate instructional materials to be used for new pedagogical methods of teaching social studies.	2.27	1.02	Disagree
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation		2.95	0.92	Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 above reveals mean and standard deviation ratings of the pedagogical methods used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools. All the items except item 7 have their mean rating scales in the region of 2.50 to 4.00; this shows that respondents agreed to the pedagogical methods used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of

social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools. The cluster has a mean of 2.95 and a standard deviation of 0.92. This implies that different pedagogical methods are used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools.

Hypothesis One:

The extent to which Social studies Curriculum content of Universal Basic Education is being implemented in JSS in Jalingo Education, Zone is not significant

Table 3: Chi-Square Test of Significance of the Extent to which Social Studies Curriculum is implemented

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.725	4	.008
Likelihood Ratio	9.942	4	.021
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.666	1	.006
N of Valid Cases	35		

Source: Field, 2021

Table 3 presents Chi-square test of significance of the extent to which Social studies Curriculum of UBE in JSS is implemented in Jalingo Education, Zone ($\chi^2 = 8.725$, $df = 4$, $p = .008$). The result shows that the extent to which Social studies Curriculum of UBE in JSS is implemented is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which says that the extent to which Social studies Curriculum content of Universal Basic Education is being implemented in JSS in Jalingo Education, Zone is not significant is rejected.

Hypothesis Two

The pedagogical methods used by social study teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of Universal Basic Education in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is not significant.

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	385.566	9	.000
Likelihood Ratio	404.143	9	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	250.736	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	376		

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 4 presents Chi-square test of significance of the pedagogical methods used by Social studies teachers in the implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in JSS in Jalingo Education, Zone ($\chi^2 = 385.566$, $df = 9$, $p = .000$). The result shows that the pedagogical methods used by Social studies teachers in the implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in JSS are significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which says that the pedagogical methods used by Social studies teachers in the implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in JSS are not significant is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of Extent to which the implementation of Social Studies curriculum of the UBE in Junior Secondary schools develop students' positive attitude. . All the items except item 2 and 6 have their mean rating scales in the region of 2.50 to 4.00; this shows that the extent to which the implementation of social studies curriculum of the UBE in Junior Secondary Schools develop students' positive attitude is high. The cluster has a mean of 3.71 and a standard deviation of 0.81. This implies that implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of the UBE in Junior Secondary Schools develops students' positive attitude. In the same vein the findings of the study affirm that of Chukwuemeka (2014) who evaluated the implementation of Social Studies curriculum in junior

secondary schools in Enugu State. The results of the study showed that the level of qualification can make a difference in the teachers who teach Social Studies and most importantly on the implementation of Social Studies curriculum in junior secondary schools. It was also discovered that Social Studies teachers employ discussion, discovery, problem-solving, inquiry and expository methods while teaching.

The findings of the study contradict the findings of Eleojo (2016) who carried out a study on the problems militating against the teaching and implementation of social studies curriculum in secondary schools in the federal capital territory, Abuja. The findings of the research revealed that, the problems against the implementation of social studies has significant effect on its implementation at secondary school levels, the perception of other social science experts significantly affects the implementation of the subject at secondary school levels, lack of materials and facilities including current textbooks, equipped library or workshop are the greatest problem affecting the implementation of social studies at the secondary school levels, there is no adequate commitment on the part of the government to ensure appropriate implementation of the social studies curriculum, the non availability of human resources significantly affects the implementation of social studies at secondary schools.

Notwithstanding the finding of this study is contrary to the findings of Jimoh (2014) in his study titled analysis of the values education component of the secondary schools social studies programme in Obalande local government in rivers state Nigeria. The result showed that over 50% of the stated instructional objectives in the secondary schools social studies curriculum were basically cognitive objectives which will serve as one of problem hindering effective implementation of social studies curriculum.

The findings of this study agrees with the findings of Adoke (2017) who studied teachers and students perceptions of social studies and teaching methods in selected junior secondary schools in the northern states of Nigeria. It was discovered that methods mainly employed were discussion and story telling methods while the problem solving approach, group method and the use of resource persons ranked the least. Furthermore, lack of trained teachers and inadequate textbooks were predominant.

The Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of the Pedagogical Methods Used by Social Studies Teachers in the Implementation of Social Studies Curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools. All the items except item 7 have their mean rating scales in the region of 2.50 to 4.00; this shows that respondents agreed to the pedagogical methods used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools. The cluster has a mean of 2.95 and a standard deviation of 0.92. This implies that different pedagogical methods are used by Social Studies teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of UBE in Junior Secondary Schools.

The finding of this study is not in line with the findings of Ubah and Shu'aibu (2014) on the evaluation of the implementation of Nigeria certificate in education social studies programme in Federal Colleges Of Education In North-Western Political Zone of Nigeria. They found that, the implementation of the course contents is mostly dominated by the use of traditional techniques of instruction notably the lecture method to the detriment of other instructional strategies

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion were made:

1. The extent to which the implementation of social studies curriculum of Universal Basic Education in Junior Secondary School develop students positive attitude in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is significant.
2. The extent to which social studies curriculum content of Universal Basic Education is being implemented in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba state is significant.
3. The pedagogical methods used by social study teachers in the implementation of social studies curriculum of Universal Basic Education in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is significant.

4. The extent to which social studies teachers used instructional materials in the implementation of social studies curriculum of Universal Basic Education in Junior Secondary School in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State is significant.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. People concerned with the implementation of social studies curriculum content should be actively involved and committed to ensure the effective implementation of social studies curriculum in Nigeria;
2. Social studies teachers need to be conversant with the appropriate and innovative teaching methods and strategies and as well employ them while teaching social studies.

REFERENCES

- Abdu-Raheem, A. (2012). Self-efficacy mechanism in human agency. *American Psychologist*, 37:122-147.
- Adeyemi, M & Ajibade, N (2016). *Issues on Curriculum*. Zaria: Sankore Educational Publisher Company Limited.
- Adoke, W. (2017). Levels of processing: A framework for memory research. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behaviour*, 11:671-684.
- Chukwuemeka. F.C. (2014). Evaluation of the implementation of the social studies curriculum in junior secondary schools in Enugu State. Unpublished M Ed Thesis. University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Eleajo, C.E. (2016). Problems militating against the teaching and implementation of Social Studies curriculum in secondary schools in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Unpublished M. Ed. Thesis, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Eya, D. (2012). *Common formative assessments*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press
- Ezeoba, P. & Okafor, D. (2019). Assessment and classroom learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy and Practice*. CARFAX, Oxford shire, Vol.5 (1): 7-74.
- Ezeoba, T. & Okafor, H. D. (2019). *Evaluation in Social Studies*. Washington, D.C.: Department of the National Education Association. p.157.
- Gabriel, M. M. (2018). A structural model for predicting Social Study achievement: Its relationship with anxiety and self-concept in Social Study. *Psychological Reports*, 86: 835-847. Africana Feb. Publishers Limited 57 Barracks road, Uyo, AkwaI bom State.
- Nzewi, G. Okpara, M. & Akudolu, J. (2015). Configural properties in sentence memory. *Journal of Verbal Learning and Verbal Behaviour*, 11: 594-605.
- Ololobou, T.M. (2017) *Creativity in context* Boulder, Co: West view press.
- Ubah, U& Shu'aibu, Y. P. S. (2014). *Introduction to the teaching of Social Studies*. Pankshin: Academic Trust Fund Publishers.
- Weiss, J. H. (2018). Analysis of citizenship goals in social studies instruction. Unpublished Ed.D. Thesis, University of Colorado.